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Report on socio- economic predictions

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1. Introduction

The Work Package 8 (WP8) of the AtlantECO project focuses on anticipating future changes in basin-scale Atlantic ecosystem services in response to environmental and socio-economic drivers. In alignment with AtlantECO's Objective 4, WP8 aims to deliver a systemic approach to support science-informed decision-making through scenario development, predictive modeling, and integrated analyses of ecosystem health and services. WP8 combines climate projections, biogeochemical models, and socio-economic analysis to evaluate risks of tipping points, regime shifts, and changes in provisioning, supporting, and regulating services such as carbon sequestration, nutrient recycling, and primary production. A significant portion of the results was already achieved prior to the official deadline and presented in previous interim reports and deliverables. However, as this is the final report, these results will be revisited and summarized in the relevant sections to ensure completeness and coherence.

WP8 is structured around four main deliverables, each addressing a critical aspect of the prediction and evaluation of ecosystem services under future climate and socio-economic scenarios. Here we report the deliverable d8.4 : **Report on socio-economic predictions:**

This report integrates economic and social projections into the ecosystem services framework. It includes macro-economic modeling using the ICES framework to simulate future trajectories of provisioning services (notably fisheries) and assesses socio-cultural values through participatory mapping and surveys. The combined economic and cultural valuation will provide a comprehensive picture of future ecosystem service trade-offs. An ancillary work proposes projections of microplastic production and diffusion in the Atlantic linked to social economic drivers of development.

2. Part 1: macroeconomic assessment

Objective

Climate change is producing a series of global ocean modifications that are resulting in unprecedented rapid impacts on various aspects of socio-ecological systems. Modification in sea level, circulation, ocean temperature, acidification and stratification are studied effects of climate change that generate impacts on many activities from coastal infrastructures (e.g. Strauss et al., 2021) to fish farms (Cao et al., 2023). In particular, the changes in primary production in terms of quantity are expected to have a pervasive effect by impacting secondary productions and thus fisheries (Tittensor et al., 2021).

However, while macroeconomic impacts of climate change on terrestrial environment have been widely investigated, the macroeconomic consequences of global warming on the ocean are largely missing. In fact, although several studies have analysed implications of rising temperature in global catches (e.g., Cheung et al., 2021; Tittensor et al., 2021; Free et al., 2022) or in the fishery sector of specific regions (e.g., Agnetta et al., 2022; Hidalgo et al., 2022; Seung and Iannelli 2016), an extensive macroeconomic analysis is still lacking (Lam et al. 2016). This last assessment is particularly challenging for two reasons. On the one hand the fish catches are and will be driven not only by biomass availability at sea, but also by social economic drivers like technology, increased demand from increasing and richer population as well as competition with other food-production sectors. On the other hand, the dynamics in the fishery sector can spill over other production sectors, like, for instance, food production, with higher order effects on the overall economic performance of a country.

To address this gap, we assess macroeconomic effects of climate change impacts on the fishery sector in the Atlantic Ocean by mid-century. We use the results from a set of global earth system models to shock a Computable General Equilibrium (CGE) macroeconomic model where we introduce biophysical constraints on the growth of fishing activities. The CGE model allows us to evaluate the economic effects on fishery prices and overall economic structure beyond the fishery sector. We control socio-economic and climatic uncertainties by considering projections from three climate models of the Coupled Model Intercomparison Project Phase 6 (CMIP6) (Eyring et al., 2016) under two Shared Socioeconomic Pathways (SSPs) (Riahi et al 2017, O'Neill et al 2015).]

Methodology and results

[Starting points for the analysis are projections for marine Net Primary Production (NPP) in Figure 1 under two different emission scenarios (SSP245 and SSP585) for the period 2040-2049. These were retrieved from three climate models belonging to the CMIP6 (Eyring et al., 2016): GFDL-ESM4 (Dunne et al., 2020, Stock et al., 2020), IPSL-CM6A-LR (Boucher et al., 2020),

MPI-ESM1-2-HR (Müller et al., 2018; Mauritsen et al., 2019). Long-term drifts in the simulated NPP were linearly removed by using the methodology extensively described in Reale et al. (2022).

The amount of NPP required to sustain fisheries exploitation by country or groups of countries in the Atlantic Ocean in the two scenarios was obtained by estimating the fishing grounds by country (Figure 2) using the SeaAroundUs (SAU) database (Pauly et al., 2020). The SAU dataset provides spatially explicit (0.5° x 0.5° resolution) reconstructions of global marine fish catches by country and species for artisanal and industrial fisheries. Here, we focused exclusively on catches (excluding illegal, unreported and unregulated catches) within the Atlantic Ocean for the period 2013-2018 to reconstruct fishing grounds also of countries that may not border the Atlantic, but conduct harvesting activities in this region, particularly in high seas areas.

The macroeconomic assessment is performed with the multi-country, multi-sector recursive-dynamic Computable General Equilibrium (CGE) ICES (Inter-temporal Computable Equilibrium System) model (Parrado and Decian 2014; Standardi et al 2023). The model has been calibrated on the Social Accounting Matrices (SAMs) of the Global Trade Analysis Project (GTAP) 10 database (Aguiar et al 2019). The SAMs record the monetary values (Mil\$ 2014) of economic exchanges taking place between different sectors, regions and agents (households, firms, governments) in 2014. In this assessment we consider 20 economic sectors and 44 regions aggregated on the basis of the most relevant Atlantic regions but also major global economic players.

In a first step we calibrate the model, initially set to replicate 2014 data, to the historical 2020. We focus on replicating GDP and population using data from the World Bank (WB, 2024) and, particularly relevant for our purposes, fishery production, using the Food and Agriculture Organization database for both marine fishery and aquaculture (FAOSTAT, 2024). This done, the experiment design consists of two further steps:

- 1) construction of socio-economic baseline scenarios without climate change impacts on NPP over the period 2020-2050,
- 2) implementation of climate change impacts on NPP in the baseline scenarios.

Our 2020-2050 socio-economic futures reflect GDP and population projections from the SSP2 and SSP5 (Riahi et al 2017, O'Neill et al 2015).

In SSP2, also defined as “middle of the road”, social, economic, and technological trends do not shift markedly from historical patterns. Development and income growth proceeds unevenly, with some countries making relatively good progress while others fall short of expectations. Global population growth is moderate and levels off in the second half of the century. However, income inequality in terms of GDP per capita between developed and developing regions improves but challenges to reducing vulnerability to societal and environmental changes remain.

In SSP5 (fossil fueled development) the world places increasing faith in competitive markets, innovation and participatory societies to produce rapid technological progress and development of human capital. These factors lead to rapid growth of the global economy, while global population peaks and declines in the 21st century. At the same time, the scenario features the exploitation of abundant fossil fuel resources and the adoption of resource and energy intensive lifestyles around the world. Because of market integration GDP per capita convergence is stronger than in SSP2. For these characteristics SSP2 has been associated with the CMIP6 scenario SSP245 featuring “average” temperature increases, while SSP5 with the most emitting CMIP6 scenario SSP585.

To increase the realism of our simulations we introduced in the ICES model explicit ecological limits to the expansion of fishery production (Costello et al., 2020; Blanchard and Novaglio, 2024; FAO, 2024). Accordingly, in SSP245 we develop three alternative cases: no constraints to, maximum 25% and maximum 10% expansion in global fishery production in the 2020-2050 period. In SSP585 we consider just two cases: no constraints to and maximum 10% expansion in global fishery production. This is because the SSP585 scenario presents a more problematic management of environmental resources that could have led to larger production expansion otherwise. Ecological limits are implemented in the model through a fishery sector-specific productivity parameter.

Overall, we build five no-climate change baseline scenarios: namely SSP245 no lim, SSP245 10% lim, SSP24 25% lim, SSP585 no lim and SSP585 10% lim.

In the second step of the simulation, we impose to the fishery sectors of the CGE model the NPP impacts computed in the ecological assessment. This required re-scaling them to match the spatial resolution of the CGE model. The final impacts on Atlantic NPP in the period 2020-2050 are shown in Table 1. Finally, as the fishery sector in the CGE model does not distinguish Atlantic and not Atlantic catches these impacts have been rescaled according to the ratio of Atlantic catches over total catches (FAO, 2020).

NPP impacts are implemented in the CGE model as changes in the productivity of the natural resource input used by the fishery sector. It can be noted that there is quite some divergence across different models. Specifically, MPI reports more severe impacts while IPSL less severe impacts. Negative impacts are also larger in the SSP585 than in the SSP245 scenario. Nonetheless, the higher penalization of Western African regions is a robust result.

Table 2 summarizes the baseline scenarios and the impact scenarios. Eventually, a total of 17 model runs are performed (5 baseline scenarios plus 12 impact scenarios). MPI-ESM1-2-HR, IPSL-CM6A-LR, GFDL-ESM4 models are abbreviated as MPI, IPSL and GFDL. A particular note refers to aquaculture. For simplicity, we assume that it is affected like marine fishery. This is because in general the aquaculture sector is highly dependent on marine fish that represents its main animal feed in the production process. In one scenario, however, labelled “SSP585 no lim GFDL Aq”, we

assumed that only marine fishery is affected. The aim of this explorative run is to assess the potential role of technological advancements in aquaculture that, by developing alternative animal feed, might mitigate the economic losses. The choice of the SSP585 no lim for the GFDL climate model derives from its more optimistic assumptions on global economic growth and technological progress.

Results and discussion

Figure 3 shows the impacts on GDP in 2050 in the twelve impact scenarios. In general, GDP follows the direction of ecological impacts, however, on a larger scale. For example, the maximum GDP loss in 2050 is around 9% in Senegal in SSP585 10% limit and MPI climate model against an impact on NPP by a bit less than 14% in the same scenario. The magnitude of these effects may surprise, considering that the fishery share over the total production is small (1.5% in the case of Senegal in 2014). Nonetheless, two mechanisms explain this result.

Firstly, there is a low substitutability between the fish natural resource and the labour and capital/energy input bundle. Accordingly, a negative shock on the natural resource is particularly costly to the firms in the sector when they try to keep the production at the pre-shock level using more labour and capital/energy input. This technological constraint in fish production drains units of labour and capital/energy from more efficient uses in other sectors.

The second mechanism concerns the fish price effect that amplifies macroeconomic losses. High fish prices increase the “economic weight” of the fishery sector that gets bigger over the years compared to other sectors in the economy. Accordingly, given that NPP losses affect a sector that is becoming progressively more important, they also induce higher aggregated indirect economic losses. This is especially true when limits are put in place in global fishery expansion.

Figure 4 focuses on the regions experiencing a GDP loss larger than 1% compared to the baseline in 2050. In the SSP245 these are just Senegal, Namibia and Western Africa. In the SSP585 the number of regions highlighting a GDP loss larger than 1% increases. The majority is from Western Africa, but now also EU and latin American regions appear. Absolute economic losses are obviously larger in the “big” Western Africa macro-region, but Namibia and Senegal with their -6% and -9% respectively stand out as the most negatively affected in percent of GDP.

The almost perfect overlap of the SSP585 no lim and the SSP585 no lim Aq scenarios, also suggest a marginal impact of aquaculture in the determination of the overall economic outcomes.

To conclude, results have shown that climate change impacts on Net Primary Production may imply substantial economic losses (>1% of GDP) by mid-century in Western African regions. This is due to three main factors: increased fish prices, climate change impacts on NPP and the nature itself of the fishery sector (low substitutability of the fish natural resource with labour, capital and energy input). For other regions uncertainty on NPP impacts is still substantial. Not surprisingly,

the scenario SSP585 with a 10% limit is the most detrimental from an economic point of view because it is the scenario with the highest increase in fish prices.

One important point in the macroeconomic assessment is that the progressive socio-economic pressure on the fish stock will determine together with a strong increase in the global fish price a change in the economic structure. If in the past decades primary sectors such as agriculture and fishery have always declined their share in the total economy, here we signal an increase in the fishery share over total production. Clearly, these results depend on our assumptions in the macroeconomic model: consumer preferences remain the same and no major technological improvement takes place in the fishery sector.

Future research will consist in separating aquaculture from marine fishery, extending the analysis to the other oceans, allowing the fishing areas to endogenously change over time in the model, enriching the technological scenarios (iron fertilization, alternative feeds for aquaculture), introducing different hypothesis on sustainable management. From the biophysical side it will be important to extend the size of the ensemble of climate models.

Figures and tables

Figure 1: Change (%) in the NPP according to GFDL-ESM4 (left column), IPSL-CM6A-LR (central column) and MPI-ESM1-2-HR (right column) for the mid-21st century time window under two different emission scenarios: SSP245 (upper panel) and SSP585 (bottom panel). Values are computed with respect to the period 1995-2014.

Figure 2: Reconstructed spatial distribution of fisheries catches (landings and discards) for selected Atlantic countries: Namibia, Norway, Senegal, and Spain. Source: SeaAroundUs project (www.searoundus.org)]

Figure 3: GDP % changes compared to the baseline scenarios in 2050

Figure 4: GDP % losses compared to the baseline scenarios in 2050 higher than 1% and associated absolute monetary losses (Billion 2014 \$) in SSP245 (top) and SSP585 (bottom)

Table1: Impacts on NPP in the Atlantic (% change in the period 2020-2050)

ICES Regions	SSP245 GFDL	SSP245 IPSL	SSP245 MPI	SSP585 GFDL	SSP585 IPSL	SSP585 4.5MPI
Baltic	0.4	2.6	-1.3	0.5	10.7	1.3
Benelux	-2.3	-1.8	-4.7	-3.3	10.5	-3.2
Canada	-2.0	-1.2	-9.0	-3.1	3.4	-7.1
CentralAmeri	-1.9	1.6	-6.7	-2.6	2.7	-6.2
China	-0.8	1.1	-5.7	-2.2	1.5	-7.0
Denmark	-1.1	-2.0	-4.6	-2.3	4.9	-3.2
EastAfrica	-0.1	-1.3	-10.8	-2.4	-1.0	-13.2
FSU	2.5	-1.2	-0.6	2.7	1.0	-2.4
Iceland	-3.1	-0.4	1.9	-4.0	11.1	4.8
Morocco	2.4	8.9	-12.4	0.6	14.2	-13.2
Namibia	-0.7	-2.3	-11.6	-2.9	-4.7	-14.1
RestAsia	-0.2	2.1	-5.6	-0.9	1.3	-6.1
RestEU Med	-4.3	-3.2	-6.8	-8.0	-3.4	-11.4
RestEurope	-2.3	0.4	-0.7	-3.5	10.4	2.1
RestLatAmer	-1.0	5.1	-4.9	-1.9	4.1	-4.6
Scandin	-1.8	4.1	-5.3	-0.5	10.6	-6.0
Senegal	-2.4	-0.2	-11.3	-5.7	-1.5	-13.7
SouthAfri	0.6	2.3	-2.0	1.6	4.2	-2.5
WestAfrica	-3.3	-3.6	-10.4	-6.8	-5.3	-13.3
arg	0.9	1.6	-2.1	1.8	1.5	-2.8
bra	1.7	4.1	-7.0	1.5	3.2	-6.3
chl	2.2	1.3	3.4	3.1	2.8	1.1
deu	-2.9	-0.7	-3.5	-3.7	11.3	-1.5
esp	-2.3	-1.7	-5.8	-4.1	4.8	-5.1
fra	-2.9	-2.5	-5.1	-4.5	6.1	-4.5
gbr	-1.1	-2.0	-1.2	-2.1	6.2	-0.2
irl	-4.1	-4.6	-5.3	-5.2	7.3	-4.6
ita	-0.7	3.8	-10.5	-3.2	6.5	-12.5
jpn	-0.5	2.0	-5.7	-0.5	1.5	-6.1
mex	0.9	9.1	-16.1	-1.3	11.2	-12.7
nor	-1.8	-0.4	1.8	-2.6	12.0	4.8
nzl	0.2	1.6	0.1	1.2	3.3	-3.1
pol	0.9	7.6	-9.3	0.9	11.5	-9.9
prt	-1.1	-3.3	-9.8	-2.8	-1.9	-10.3
rus	-2.6	0.1	-1.9	-4.0	10.4	0.7
usa	0.0	5.4	-12.2	-1.1	8.8	-10.0
xoc	-0.9	4.0	-5.5	0.3	1.6	-5.8

Note: countries within each ICES region and acronyms are explained in Table A1 in Annex 3.

Table 2: Baseline and impact scenarios

No climate change scenarios	Impact scenarios
1. SSP245 no lim	1. SSP245 no lim GFDL
2. SSP245 25% lim	2. SSP245 25% lim GFDL 3. SSP245 25% lim MPI 4. SSP245 25% lim IPSL
3. SSP245 10% lim	5. SSP245 10% lim GFDL 6. SSP245 10% lim MPI 7. SSP245 10% lim IPSL
4. SSP585 no lim	8. SSP585 GFDL no lim 9. SSP585 GFDL no lim Aq
5. SSP585 10 %	10. SSP585 10% lim GFDL 11. SSP585 10% lim MPI 12. SSP585 10% lim IPSL

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3. Part 2: socio economic projections

The future levels of microplastics pollution in the oceans are closely tied to global trends in GDP and population growth. These drivers are core components of the Shared Socioeconomic Pathways (SSPs), which outline different trajectories for society, economy, and environment. The future of microplastics pollution in the oceans is shaped by the combined effects of GDP growth, population increase, and urbanisation rate, all of which are closely tied to plastic consumption, waste generation, and the effectiveness of waste management systems. Under the Shared Socioeconomic Pathways (SSP) scenarios, SSP1 (sustainability), SSP2 (middle-of-the-road), and SSP3 (regional rivalry/high challenges). These the trajectories for these three variables differ substantially, resulting in distinct outcomes for microplastics pollution by 2050 and 2070.

Urbanisation rate, alongside GDP and population growth, is a major driver of future microplastics pollution in the world's oceans (Reshadi, et al., 2025; Lee et al., 2024; Jahandar, 2023). As urban areas expand, they become concentrated sources of plastic consumption and waste generation, with urban landscapes acting as major sources and stormwater runoff serving as a principal pathway for microplastics to enter aquatic environments (Ihenetu et al., 2023). Studies have demonstrated a positive correlation between microplastics concentrations and factors such as population density, GDP density, and the percentage of built-up land use, all of which are closely tied to urbanisation. As cities grow and develop, the increased use and disposal of plastic products result in higher levels of plastic pollution (Lee et al., 2024; Jahandar, 2023).

Methodology

Data: The main source of the microplastics data was Seville et al. (2015), augmented with data retrieved from 16 additional cruises. Data include counts of small plastics with a size <5 mm gathered using a range of nets with varying mesh sizes. All data were converted from numbers and concentrations per volume or area into concentrations per km² using the conversion routines as documented in Kulkera et al. (2012). All microplastics data were retrieved from the literature and combined with the global collection by Seville et al., (2015) for small plastics (microplastics mostly < 5 mm in diameter). The data were converted to units of number of particles per km² and total mass per km² using conversion routines following Kukulka et al., (2012). First, this deliverable identifies socioeconomic stressors that are relevant for the evolution of marine

ecosystems health. Second, consistently with the storylines provided by the Shared Social Economic Pathways (Riahi et al. 2017), projections are computed for two future time periods.

Future GDP and population data: We use projected GDP and population data from Wang and Sun (2022). The authors use LitPop approach to downscale the GDP projections for five SSPs to a 1km×1km spatial resolution. GDP projections were based on national projections for 177 countries and supranational projections for the world regions. GDP and GRP projections were then generated using these GDP growth rates and official figures from 2005 to complete the data series and ensure global consistency for all five SSPs. For the population projections, the authors use the spatial distribution pattern in the Landscan population dataset for 2015. The two population projections were mosaiced together to create a new population raster for 2030–2100 at 10-year intervals for the five SSPs.

Empirical analysis

We start with simple regressions using gridded average microplastics concentrations data as the dependent variable, GDP, GDP per capita, and urbanisation (land use change). We control for grid-cell and year fixed-effects. Microplastics data were spatially merged with gridded GDP per capita data using the elliptical method with a threshold of 200KM from the nearest grid-cell (Dasgupta et al., 2021).

Higher GDP generally leads to increased consumption of plastics, unless accompanied by strong policy and technological advances. Economic growth without sustainability measures leads to more plastic production and, consequently, more microplastics entering the oceans. Higher population and population density result in higher plastic consumption use and waste generation, especially in rapidly urbanising and developing regions. Population increases, especially in the coastal zones are especially impactful in scenarios with weak waste management systems. Urbanisation acts as a powerful multiplier of microplastics pollution. As urbanisation increases, they concentrate both the use and disposal of plastics, especially often outpacing the development of adequate waste management and wastewater treatment infrastructure. This leads to higher emissions of microplastics into rivers and, ultimately, the oceans.

We thus compute the impact of future socioeconomic scenarios three SSP narratives (SSP1, SSP2, and SSP3) trajectories mentioned above. Using the delta change method (Dasgupta,

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2018), we combine the empirical estimates from Table 1 with three socioeconomic scenarios. This consists in comparing each scenario's projections (2031 - 2050 and 2051 - 2070) against its own simulation of the historical period (1996 – 2005) and computing the change in microplastics pollution.

1. SSP1 (Sustainability - Taking the Green Road): This pathway envisions a world moving towards sustainability, with low population growth, rapid technological progress (especially in green solutions), strong international cooperation, and a focus on reduced consumption and resource efficiency. This scenario aims for a global warming target of 1.5-2°C.
2. SSP2 (Middle of the Road): This scenario represents a continuation of historical trends. It features intermediate population growth, moderate technological change, and regional rather than strong global cooperation. This pathway leads to moderate climate change.
3. SSP3 (Regional Rivalry - A Rocky Road): This scenario depicts a fragmented world with high population growth, uneven economic development, and limited international cooperation. Prioritization of national or regional interests over global sustainability leads to significant challenges for climate change mitigation and adaptation. This pathway results in high greenhouse gas emissions and substantial global warming.

Results

Our findings (see Table 1) show that increases in urbanisation and GDP per capita have statistically significant increase on microplastics pollution. As more urbanised and economically active regions tend to generate more plastic waste, and, without effective interventions, a greater share of this waste enters aquatic environments such as rivers and oceans.

Projections (see Figure 1) indicate that, without significant policy changes, global microplastics pollution will increase, depending on the socioeconomic trajectory realised - substantially. Even under SSP1, which assumes more sustainable economic and urban growth alongside ambitious policy measures, microplastics pollution is projected to increase by approximately 220% on average by 2051-2070 compared to the baseline period (Figure 1). However, even in this best-case scenario, legacy plastics already present in the environment will continue to fragment and contribute to microplastics pollution for decades, making reductions in total ocean concentrations unlikely.

Under SSP2, which reflects moderate economic growth and urbanisation without transformative policy interventions, microplastics pollution is projected to increase by nearly 105% (40.9% by 2031-2050) on average between 2051-2070. This scenario is characterised by rapid urbanisation in developing regions, where sewer connections and urban infrastructure expand faster than wastewater treatment capacity, resulting in higher emissions of microplastics to rivers and oceans (Bukovsky et al., 2021).

In the more extreme SSP3 scenario, which is characterised by high population and urbanisation growth combined with generally weak governance and minimal improvements in waste management, microplastics pollution is projected to increase by 220% by 2051-2070. Under this scenario, the substantial growth of urbanisation, especially in lower-income countries, would drive a dramatic increase in plastic use and waste, with relatively low capacity to manage such waste effectively (Chen et al., 2022).

Several coastal locations around the world have been identified as having particularly high levels of microplastics pollution, affecting both environmental and human health. Coastal locations projected to experience the highest increases in microplastics pollution under SSP scenarios include the West African coast, the densely populated and rapidly urbanising shores of South and Southeast Asia, and the Mediterranean coastline. South and Southeast Asian coastal regions, including the Ganges-Brahmaputra Delta, are also at high risk, driven by high population density, rapid urbanisation, industrial runoff, and seasonal monsoon flooding that accelerates microplastics transport to the ocean. The Mediterranean Sea, which already contains a disproportionately high share of global microplastics, is projected to experience one of the highest increases in microplastics pollution by 2070. These projections are expected to be higher in regions where urbanisation will likely outpace improvements in wastewater treatment and waste management, and where hydrological conditions, such as monsoons or heavy rainfall, facilitate the rapid transport of plastics from land to sea (IPCC, 2022).

Discussion

Higher GDP and urbanisation lead to greater plastic consumption and waste generation, while rapid population growth amplifies these effects (Fiore et al., 2022). Urbanisation accelerates the impact of population growth on pollution, especially where infrastructure is lagging. In scenarios

with rapid urbanisation but slow improvement in waste management, microplastics pollution inputs to rivers and seas are projected to increase substantially by 2050 and 2070 compared to the baseline period. Only in the most ambitious sustainability scenario (SSP1), where urbanisation is managed alongside advanced treatment and source reduction, can microplastics pollution be stabilised. Without mitigation policies such as adoption of advanced wastewater treatment, riverine interception systems, and strict plastic use regulations. These coastal hotspots will experience potentially irreversible ecological impacts from microplastics pollution by the end of the century.

There are certain limitations in our analysis include. Our projection isolates the impact of changes in GDP per capita and urbanisation compared to the simulated historical baseline period for each of the socioeconomic scenarios. As such, we do not project the overall increase in microplastics pollution. Additionally, lack of data on fishing activities and tourism means that the projected increase in microplastics pollution is likely an underestimate. On the other hand, our analysis does not account for explicit policies to reduce microplastics pollution or behavioural changes.

In summary, the urbanisation rate is as significant as GDP and population growth in determining the future scale of microplastics pollution in the oceans. Without coordinated action to improve waste management and reduce plastic use, rapid urbanisation will result in at least a doubling of microplastics pollution by 2070 in many regions. Sustainable urban planning and major investments in wastewater treatment are essential to prevent urbanisation from further accelerating the flow of microplastics into the world's oceans

	(1)	(2)
Log of GDP	0.142**	
	(0.036)	
Log of GDP per capita		0.229**
		(0.016)
Urbanisation	0.614**	0.896***
	(0.017)	(0.003)
Robust p-values in parentheses		
*** p<0.01, ** p<0.05, * p<0.1		

Table 1: Regression results

Figure 1: Changes in microplastic concentration in SSP1 (upper map) SSP2 (middle map) SSP 3 (lower map) in response to socioeconomic stressors (2051 – 2070 vs “today”)

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4. Part 3: Genomic Insights into Socio-economic Impacts of Plankton Biogeography Shifts

We present here results from the article by Frémont et al. (2022), focusing specifically on socio-economic impacts. Other aspects of this study have already been discussed in the section corresponding to Deliverable 8.1 of the project report.

The study reveals that by the end of the century (2090–2099), under the high-emission scenario RCP8.5, approximately 60% of the studied oceanic surface south of 60°N is projected to experience a change in the dominant planktonic province across at least one organism size fraction. This large-scale reorganization primarily manifests as a poleward shift of temperate provinces and an expansion of tropical provinces, driven predominantly by increases in sea surface temperature (SST), which accounts for 50% of the variance, followed by changes in phosphate (11%) and salinity (10.3%).

This biogeographical restructuring carries significant socio-economic implications, particularly for regions engaged in marine resource exploitation. Exclusive Economic Zones (EEZs), which are critical for national fisheries and marine governance, are expected to be substantially affected, with 42.2% to 55.2% of their surface areas experiencing a shift in community assemblages compared to the present day. Similarly, major fisheries zones are projected to undergo ecological transformation over 41.8% to 51.8% of their area, suggesting potential disruptions in species distributions, trophic interactions, and resource availability.

In terms of biogeochemical consequences, the restructuring of planktonic provinces is associated with a projected average decrease of approximately 4% in carbon export fluxes. This reduction is linked to observed compositional shifts in key functional plankton groups. Notably, an increase in diazotrophic cyanobacteria in tropical and equatorial zones and a decrease in nano-diatoms and nano-algae, particularly within subtropical and equatorial latitudes, were identified as contributing factors. These changes may diminish the efficiency of the biological carbon pump and alter nutrient cycling processes.

Altogether, the results emphasize that climate-driven shifts in plankton biogeography will not only influence ecological dynamics and biogeochemical processes but would also have direct and indirect ramifications for human activities reliant on ocean ecosystems. These findings underscore the need for anticipatory governance and adaptive management strategies in marine socio-ecological systems facing global change.

5. Conclusions and Perspectives

Deliverable D8.4 develops an integrated socio-economic forward-looking assessment of Atlantic ecosystem-service vulnerability, by linking biophysical change (notably changes in Net Primary Production, NPP, and plankton biogeography) to economic outcomes (fisheries sector and GDP impacts), societal drivers of pressure (microplastics), and exposure of managed marine areas (EEZs and major fisheries zones) to climate-driven ecological reorganization. The deliverable's main contribution is to make explicit that future risks to ocean services arise from coupled dynamics: climate impacts on marine productivity interact with market mechanisms, management constraints, and socio-economic development pathways, producing non-linear and regionally concentrated outcomes.

A first key result is the macroeconomic evidence that climate-driven changes in NPP can translate into macroeconomic losses that are disproportionate to the current share of fisheries in GDP, because (i) fishing production exhibits low substitutability between the natural resource input and other factors, and (ii) fish price amplification increases the economy-wide weight of the sector over time. The analysis highlights Western Africa (including Senegal and Namibia) as consistently among the most exposed regions by mid-century, with GDP losses exceeding 1% in several scenarios, and larger impacts under high-emission and tighter ecological constraints on fisheries expansion.

Second, D8.4 quantifies how socio-economic trajectories shape an additional, largely independent pressure: microplastics pollution. Empirical relationships indicate statistically significant positive effects of urbanisation and GDP per capita on microplastics concentrations, and scenario-based projections suggest substantial increases by mid- to late-century across SSPs, largest under SSP3, but still markedly increasing even under SSP1, reflecting inertia from legacy plastics and delayed benefits of mitigation. The deliverable identifies coastal hotspots likely to face the steepest increases where rapid urbanisation outpaces waste and wastewater infrastructure.

Third, by reframing plankton biogeography projections through a socio-economic lens, D8.4 shows that climate-driven reorganization of plankton provinces is expected to affect a large fraction of EEZs and major fisheries zones, with implications for resource availability, governance, and the stability of provisioning services. It also links this reorganization to an expected decline in carbon export, emphasizing that socio-economic impacts can emerge both through fisheries pathways and through changes in regulating services.

Perspectives

Priority next steps for D8.4 are to: (1) move from exogenous fishing grounds to endogenous adaptation (redistribution of effort, shifting access, and management responses), including explicit separation of marine fisheries vs aquaculture and alternative feed/technology pathways; (2) extend socio-economic pressure projections by incorporating policy levers (waste

management, wastewater treatment, plastic regulation) and additional drivers (tourism, maritime transport, fishing activity) to reduce bias in microplastics projections; (3) strengthen the coupling between biophysical change and economics via more explicit food-web and stock dynamics (beyond NPP shocks) and larger climate-model ensembles; and (4) operationalize outputs as regional risk narratives and indicators for decision support (e.g., Western African exposure as a robust cross-cutting signal), including uncertainty ranges across climate models, SSPs, and ecological-constraint assumptions. Overall, D8.4 provides a coherent basis for translating Atlantic climate-driven ecosystem change into socio-economic risk and prioritizing adaptation and mitigation options at regional scales.

6. Annexes

Table A1 of D8.4 : list of regions and corresponding countries in the macroeconomic ICES model

ICES No.	Regions	Countries
1	RestWorld	American Samoa, Bouvet Island, British Indian Ocean Territory, Cook Islands, Federated States of Micronesia, Fiji, French Polynesia, French Southern Territories, Guam, Kiribati, Marshall Islands, Nauru, New Caledonia, Niue, Northern Mariana Islands, Palau, Papua New Guinea, Pitcairn, Samoa, Solomon Islands, Tokelau, Tonga, Tuvalu, United States Minor Outlying Islands, Vanuatu, Wallis and Futuna Islands
2	aus	Australia, Christmas Island, Cocos (Keeling) Islands, Heard Island and McDonald Islands, Norfolk Island
3	China	China, Hong Kong
4	India	India
5	jpn	Japan
6	nzl	New Zeland
7	RestAsia	Afghanistan, Bangladesh, Bhutan, Brunei Darussalam, Cambodia, Chinese Taipei, Indonesia, Laos, Macao, Malaysia, Maldives, Mongolia, Myanmar, Nepal, North Korea, Pakistan, Philippines, Singapore, South Korea, Sri Lanka, Thailand, Timor-Leste, Viet Nam
8	Canada	Canada
9	usa	United States of America
10	mex	Mexico
11	RestLatAmer	Bolivia, Colombia, Ecuador, Falkland Islands (Malvinas), French Guiana, Guyana, Paraguay, Peru, South Georgia and the South Sandwich Islands, Suriname, Uruguay, Venezuela
12	CentralAmeri	Anguilla, Antigua and Barbuda, Aruba, Bahamas, Barbados, Belize, Bermuda, British Virgin Islands, Cayman Islands, Costa Rica, Cuba, Dominica, Dominican Republic, El Salvador, Grenada, Guatemala, Haiti, Honduras, Jamaica, Montserrat, Netherlands Antilles, Nicaragua, Panama, Puerto Rico, Saint Kitts and Nevis, Saint Lucia, Saint Vincent and Grenadines, Trinidad and Tobago, Turks and Caicos Islands, Virgin Islands (US)
13	arg	Argentina
14	bra	Brazil
15	chl	Chile
16	Benelux	Belgium, Luxembourg, Netherlands
17	Baltic	Estonia, Latvia, Lithuania
18	France	France
19	Germany	Germany

20	RestEUMed	Croatia, Cyprus, Greece, Malta, Slovenia
21	Ireland	Ireland
22	Italy	Italy
23	pol	Poland
24	prt	Portugal
25	RomaBulga	Bulgaria, Romania
26	Spain	Spain
27	Denmark	Denmark
28	Scandin	Finland, Sweden
29	gbr	United Kingdom
30	CentralEU	Austria, Czech Republic, Hungary, Slovakia
31	nor	Norway
32	che	Switzerland
33	RestEurope	Albania, Andorra, Bosnia and Herzegovina, Faroe Islands, Gibraltar, Guernsey, Isle of Man, Jersey, Monaco, Montenegro, North Macedonia, San Marino, Serbia, Vatican City State
34	Iceland	Iceland
35	FSU	Armenia, Azerbaijan, Belarus, Georgia, Kazakhstan, Kyrgyzstan, Moldova, Tajikistan, Turkmenistan, Ukraine, Uzbekistan
36	rus	Russian Federation
37	Morocco	Morocco
38	NorthAfrica	Algeria, Egypt, Libya, Tunisia, Western Sahara
39	MiddleEast	Bahrain, Irak, Iran, Israel, Jordan, Kuwait, Lebanon, Oman, Palestinian Territory, Qatar, Saudi Arabia, Syria, Turkey, United Arab Emirates, Yemen
40	Senegal	Senegal
41	Namibia	Namibia
42	WestAfrica	Angola, Benin, Burkina Faso, Cameroon, Cape Verde, Central African Republic, Chad, Congo, Cote d'Ivoire, Democratic Republic of the Congo, Equatorial Guinea, Gabon, Gambia, Ghana, Guinea, Guinea-Bissau, Liberia, Mali, Mauritania, Niger, Nigeria, Saint Helena, Sao Tome and Principe, Sierra Leone, Togo
43	EastAfrica	Botswana, Burundi, Comoros, Djibouti, Eritrea, Ethiopia, Kenya, Madagascar, Malawi, Mauritius, Mayotte, Mozambique, Rwanda, Seychelles, Somalia, Sudan, Tanzania, United Republic of Uganda, Zambia, Zimbabwe
44	SouthAfri	Eswatini, Lesotho, South Africa

